

Editorial Board for the Asian Resonance

July - 2017

PATRON

Dr. M.D. Pathak
Chairman, Centre for Research &
Development of Waste & Marginal Land
Ex. Director General, U.P. Council of
Agriculture Research, U.P.
Ex. Director, Research and Training,
International Rice Research Institute,
Manila, Philippines
pathakmd1@gmail.com

EDITOR

Dr. Rajeev Misra
Secretary,
Social Research Foundation,
Kanpur
indra.rajeev@gmail.com
asianresonance@gmail.com

EXECUTIVE BOARD

Dr. Asha Tripathi
Senior Vice-President,
Social Research Foundation,
Kanpur
asha23346@gmail.com

Mrs. Nandini Upadhyay
Associate Professor,
Dayanand College of Law,
Kanpur

EDITORIAL-ADVISORY BOARD

Library Science

Dr. U. C. Shukla
Fiji National University,
Lautoka, Fiji

Political Science and International Relation

Professor Vandana Asthana
Eastern Washington University,
Cheney, WA 99004

Anthropology

Dr. K Bharathi
Arba Minch University,
Arba Minch, Ethiopia,
North Africa

Chemistry

Dr. Narendra Bhojak
MGS University,
Bikaner, Rajasthan
Dr. Sumnesh
Govt. Degree College,
Jammu, J & K

Geography

Dr. Vinod Singh
Govt. Dungar College,
Bikaner, Rajasthan
Dr. Pinku Suthar
Govt. P.G. College, Jodhpur

History

Manohar Kumar
Saltora Netaji Centenary College,
Saltora, West Bengal
Dr. Anila Purohit
Govt. Dungar College,
Bikaner, Rajasthan

Management

Dr. Suresh Seth
Rayat Institute of Management,
Raikot, Punjab
Dr. K.C. Biswal
Nehru Tura Campus Tura,
Meghalaya
Dr. Rajiv Aggarwal
Vardhman College,
Bijnor, U.P.

Commerce

Swapan Kumar Samanta
Sonomukhi College,
Sonomukhi, West Bengal
Dr. Praveen Sahu
Central University of Rajasthan,
Ajmer

Economics

Dr. Anup Kumar Mishra
DAV PG College (B.H.U.), Varanasi
Dr. Mona Khare
NUEPA, New Delhi

Psychology

Dr. Chandra Shekhar
University of Jammu,
Jammu-Tawi, J & K
Dr. Anuradha Singh
M.K.P. (P.G.) College,
Dehradun, U.K.

Botany

Dr. Debnath Palit
Durgapur Government College,
Durgapur, West Bengal.
Dr. Sanjay Pandey
Banwarilal Bhalotia College,
Asansol, West Bengal

Zoology

Dr. Prakash Chandra Acharya
Guru Govind Govt. College,
Banswara, Rajasthan
Dr. Devendra Nath Pandey
Govt. S.K.N.P.G.College,
Mauganj, Rewa, M.P.

Applied Science

Mr. M.G. Mohanan
Vivek College, Sidhartha Nagar,
Goregoun, (West) Mumbai

16.	Invitro Induction of Shoot In Medicinally Important Plant <i>Hybanthus Enneaspermus</i> (Linn.) Prashant K Patankar & Sanjay R Biradar Osmanabad, Maharashtra	106-108
17.	Amount of Selected Heavy Metals (Cu, Mn, Zn, Ni and Cr) on Different Age Series Over Burden Dumps in Sonepur Bazare Coalmine Under Raniganj Coalfield Area, West Bengal. Chanchal Kumar Biswas, Asansol, West Bengal.	109-113
18.	Values and Materialism Dilemma in College Teachers of Punjab Ashutosh Sharma, Hardeep Kaur, Kapurthala, Gagan Deep Sharma, New Delhi & Jagmeet Bawa, Kapurthala	114-120
19.	A Study on Radiation and Cadmium Induced Biochemical Changes in the Jejunum of Mice Mamta Jain, R.K. Purohit, Urmila Khatri, K.M.Bhartiya & M.L.Gupta, Bikaner	121-127
20.	Fungal Diversity of Kshipra River with Relation to Human Health Shivi Bhasin, Arvind N Shukla, & Sharad Shrivastava, Ujjain, M.P.	128-134
21.	Adulteration in Local Available Milk Samples of Jabalpur Regions –A Comparative Study M. Pouranik, A Siddiqua, S. Sarkhel & M.Tripathi, Jabalpur, M.P.	135-139
22.	Analysis of Settlement Patterns through NNA Technique in Bangar and Aravalli Regions of Rajasthan Leela Kumari & Vinod Singh, Bikaner	140-145
23.	A Study on the Social Well Being of Rice Mill Workers in Burdwan City and Adjoining Areas, West Bengal, India Papia Nandy Palit, Barjora, Bankura	146-150
24.	Water Scarcity and Health Hazards in Changing Climate Scenario: A Case Study of a Semi-Arid Area in Rajasthan Anshuman Upadhyaya, Lucknow & Subhakanta Mohapatra, New Delhi	151-157
25.	Contextualizing the Status of Women in India Sanjay Prasad, Saltora, West Bengal	158-163
26.	Emotional Maturity: Intelligence and Academic Streams Ayesha Begum & Archana Satsangi, Agra	164-169
27.	Influence of Achievement Motivation on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students Chandra Shekhar, Jammu-Tawi, J & K & Priya Choudhary, Udhampur, J & K	170-174
28.	Psycho-Geographical Study of Mental Health, Well-Being and Perceived Stress among Students Belonging to Urban and Rural Areas of Chandigarh Shilpa Singh Rohilla, Ravinder Singh, Chandigarh & Dipti Batra, Landran, Punjab	175-180
29.	The Narrative Influence of Mangalkavya in Chitta Sinha's Novels Pallab Kumar Sadhu, West Bengal	181-185
30.	Re-visioning the Diasporic Dilemma: Narrating 'Home' and Composite Identities Gurudev Meher, Cuttack, Odisha	186-192

The Narrative Influence of Mangalkavya in Chitta Sinha's Novels

Abstract

From the very inception of Bengali Literature writing, Indian cultural heritage has been a significant influence on the writers. It is also a source of inspiration for them because the Puranas provided them with varied source materials. As such, the Mangalkavya is one such adaptation of the Puranas. Therefore Mangalkavya reflected the socio-cultural aspects of the pre-colonial as well as ancient period in India. Despite the colonial hangover Bengali Literature has been successful in reiterating its identity through the pre-colonial tradition. In this regard Chitta Sinha's novels are a very important instance of literature deriving its source material and narrative framework from Mangalkavya. The narratives of Chitta Sinha's novel therefore express and represent the quest for self-discovery, socio-economic status, ancient heritage and culture of the ancient period. The narratives therefore create a fusion of the ancient and the modern in its representation.

Keywords: Novel, Mangalkavya, Puranas, Ancient heritage, Narrative, Self-discovery, Indian Culture, pre-colonial, society, Folk culture, Chitta Sinha.

Introduction

During the Middle Ages MangalKavya significantly influenced the literature of the time. Over the years the different aspects of MangalKavya like the characters, plot, narrative ingredients have been used and employed in different narratives of literature. Therefore it is imperative to note here that MangalKavya's influence in Bengali literature including Poetry, Short stories and Novel is immense. The narratives of Mangalkavya which were written from 13th century to the 18th century (Manasamangal, Chandimangal, Dharmamangal, Annadamangal) have left an indelible mark on present literature, for this reason those narratives are now more open to analysis and interpretation. Reception of the MangalKavya varies in the two halves of the 20th century. While on the second half of the 20th century the narratives of Mangalkavya were vigorously followed whereas in the first half the narratives of MangalKavya were adapted by many authors. These types of composition are Dinesh Chandra Sen's *Behula* (1907) and *Phullora* (1907), Bhudhar Chandra Gangopadhyay's *Khullana ba Marta loke Chandir Puja Prachar* (1910), Haripada Chattopadhyay's *Khullana* (1911), Batokrishna Pal's *Srimanta Saudagor* (1912), Chandrakanta Dutta Saraswati Bidyabhusan's *Kalketu* (1923). In the second half of the 20th century, many novels were written keeping in mind the narratives of Manasamangal, Chandimangal, Dharmamangal, and Annadamangal. Writers like Mahasweta Devi, Tarasankar Bandopadhyay, Chitta Sinha, Narayan Gangopadhyay, Avijit Sen Amiyobhusan Majumdar, Selina Hossain wrote their novels keeping in mind the narratives of Mangalkavya. Although most of these novels were inspired by MangalKavya, at the very outset these novels have also become unique forms of art.

Aim of the Study

The significance of these texts being inspired by MangalKavya is also related with the scope and nature of modern Bengali literature. The critic Asru Kumar Sikhdar questions the relevance and emergence of Puranas in modern literature and also questions the tendency to return to these old narratives for inspiration. In this context Asru Kumar Sikhdar argues that modern literature often resorts to old Puranic aspects to reflect and project modern tendencies.¹ For instance the fire trial or Agnipariksha of Sita or the disrobing of Draupadi or the injustice done to Eklavya etc. are used to convey modern the different aspects of the modern situation. George Steener called this "repeatability". Asru Kumar Sikhdar argues:

Pallab Kumar Sadhu

Research Scholar,
Deptt. of Bengali,
Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan,
West Bengal